

**A STUDY OF THE DIFFICULTIES IN WRITING ENGLISH ESSAYS OF XII
STANDARD STUDENTS OF ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL AND
TO SUGGEST THE REMEDIES.**

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Abstract: -

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The students of junior colleges, who have learnt English from the first standard as the first language also face difficulties in writing essays. They are able to communicate in English but not quiet correct in expressing their views on any topic creatively. They commit number of errors like spellings, punctuation marks, grammar, vocabulary etc. In the world of globalization and as English is a universal language the above study will definitely help to understand the difficulties faced by XII std students and through certain remedial programmes, one can develop their essay writing skill.

Key-Words- *Essay, free composition, remedial programme, Errors*

1.1. Introduction –

As an English teacher, the researcher has experience of more than thirty years in the field of teaching English & felt that the position of English language in secondary and higher secondary schools is not satisfactory. The problem of English language is not only with the students of Marathi medium schools of Maharashtra, but also with those students who have learnt in English medium schools upto tenth std. and studied English as a first language.

Particularly, these students of English medium institutions, face difficulties in writing essays. They are able to communicate in English but not quite correct in Writing English. Now a days the students are not inclined to writing essays as they find it a tedious task. Their essays are not upto the mark. There are number of spelling mistakes, grammatical errors in their written essays. It is because they do not have reading habit. Most of the time, they are preoccupied with doing homework, attending tuition classes, browsing the internet or giving their leisure time on the face book. Their main objective is just to clear the annual examination. It's now easy to score in the examination by reproducing borrowed material. That's why even the students of Junior Colleges, do not have any creativity or originality in writing essays.

1.2 Need and Importance of the study –

In the 21st century, we are already living in the world of technology and globalization. As English is a world language, we can't deny its importance. Effective communication is the result of good command over language. But good command over language comes through proper use of vocabulary and correct uses of tenses or grammar. So if students have ability to express their views, thoughts, feelings in a good, expressive and lucid language, they will be able to communicate fluently and correctly. Such kind of researches are beneficial to the teachers and students to know better English for the use of speaking reading, writing etc.

1.3 Research Problem- Statement-

A study of the difficulties in writing English Essays of XII std. students of English medium school and to suggest the remedies.

1.4 Objectives of the research –

- To identify the difficulties faced by the XII std. students of science in writing English essays.
- To identify weak students of XII std. students of science in writing English essays.

- To find out the causes of facing difficulties of XII std. students of science in writing English essays.
- To analyze the difficulties of XII std students of science in writing English essays.
- To implement the remedial programmes to overcome the difficulties in writing English Essays of XII std. students of science.

- To compare the errors through pretest and post test in writing English essays of the XII std. students of science.
- To suggest the remedies to overcome the difficulties in writing English essays of std XII students of science faculty.

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1.5 **Hypothesis** – If the students get exposure through remedial measures, they can write better Essays in English.

1.6 **Operational definitions of the terms** –

- a) Study – The study for finding out the abilities of Jr. College students of science in writing English essays.
- b) Essay – Essays written at school or Jr. College were trial exercises or attempts at expressing students thoughts in good English.
- c) Types of essays – Free and guided composition or essays, which were given for practice in writing English language.

- d) Difficulties – The students faced problems in writing ideal essays in good English
- e) Std XII – The students who had passed their XI std and had been admitted for further studies in second year of Junior College in science stream.
- f) Writing Essay – Students were expected to write essay in English on a particular subject giving expression to their own personal ideas and feelings, opinions on the given topic.
- g) Remedies – Activities which were conducted to rectify the difficulties in writing essays in English. Means to find solutions to the problems of writing essays in English language.

1.7 **Scope and Limitations** –

- 1) Only XII std. students of science faculty from one junior college were selected.
- 2) The students both were selected – Boys and Girls but were not separately studied or analyzed.
- 3) Only 50 students of one science division of XII standard were selected.
- 4) Some students were admitted in XII std of science division from vernacular medium schools, which were not separately analyzed.
- 5) The students were from one Junior College which was attached to secondary English medium school.
- 6) The students of science faculty were selected and not commerce or Arts faculties.
- 7) Free composition or essays were selected as tool for collecting data from the students.

1.8 **Review of related literature** –

Review was taken for understanding and learning the art of writing Good essays in English. Reading related literature on the aspects of good writing helped the students of std XII of science faculty to improve their essay writing skill and consequently to express their thoughts and views in an effective manner.

1.9 **Types of Essays** –

The topics were selected on the basis of types of essays like Reflective, Narrative, Descriptive, Expository and Imaginative one. These were used as Research Tool.

1.10 **Characteristics of Good Essay** –

It was decided because that helped to evaluate the essay objectively and to analyze the data.

1. **Unity** – An essay must have unity, developing one theme with a definite purpose and in a variety of ways from different points of views.
2. **Order** – It should follow certain ordered line of thought and come to a definite conclusion.
3. **Brevity** – Essays of students of Higher Secondary school should not be too long. It must have limit of minimum 300 to 400 words. It should be brief exercise and concisely expressed.
4. **Style** – It should be dignified and literary. High flowery language must be avoided. It should be simple, direct, clear and natural. The secret of clear writing is clear thinking which should be reflected through the writing style of students.
5. **The personal touch** – It should reflect the writer's individuality and personal feelings.

These five characteristic also were thought for evaluating the students written essays in pretest as well as post test.

1.11 **Research Methodology** – For the collection of data, descriptive survey research method was selected.

1.12 As a research tool –

Topics related to the XII std. curriculum of English language subject for English medium students regarding free composition, the following topics were used as research tool.

- i.e. 1) My ambition
2) Journey by train
3) Save the environment
4) My idea of developed India.
5) Uses and misuses of mobile
6) Internet: Boon or Curse

1.13 Research Procedure –

Students from one division of XII std. of Science faculty were selected with the permission of Head master of English medium school. There were fifty students, so all were selected through a purposive sampling method. They were given sheets to write their name, standard, division and the medium in which they had learned upto X std. Some of the students who were admitted in XI and XII std. of science division were of vernacular medium school. They were given one hour to write free composition out of given six topics on any one topic. That was pre test. Under the researcher's observation, the students wrote free essay on one topic of their choice.

Then the pretest was assessed and the errors in English writing were noted down and analyzed. The criteria for assessment as it was decided were followed. Their scores were counted and tabulated. Total numbers of errors were also calculated. Then for five periods, the researcher guided them, how to write free composition with the characteristics of good essays in English. Some essays for writing purpose were given for practice to the students. Then after five days remedial program the researcher conducted the same test as post – test of writing free essay

in English language. The students actively participated. Then post-tests were also assessed and analyzed. The problems, errors were identified, counted and analyzed mean, percentages were used for calculation purpose and the data was analyzed with above simple statistical tools. And conclusions were drawn.

1.14 **Data Analysis and Interpretation** –

1) Criteria 1 – Grammar

For Grammar: 2 Marks were allotted

Table No. 1	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	0.8	1.1

Interpretation –

The score for grammar obtained in the post test by the students were 1.1 and the score in pre-test was 0.8 which was less than post test score in grammatical structure.

Conclusion –

The above mean score in the post test showed improvement in the uses of grammar after the remedial measures were taken.

2) Criteria 2 – Vocabulary: 2 Marks

Table No. 2	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	0.8	1.3

Interpretation –

The score for vocabulary obtained in the post test were 1.3 and the score in pre test was 0.8 which was again less than post test score in the uses of vocabulary.

Conclusion – The above mean score in the post test showed improvement in their language skill by using appropriate words, vocabulary, correct spellings with correct expressions.

3) Criteria 3 – Content Matter : 2 Marks

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Table No.3	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	1.0	1.4

Interpretation –

The score for content matter obtained in the post test were 1.4 which was increased than the score of pre test which was 1.0 only.

Conclusions –

The above score showed that the students had taken extra efforts to read reference books from the school library and to obtain related literature from other sources.

4) **Criteria 4** – Organization and Presentation : 2 Marks

Table No.4	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	0.8	1.2

Interpretation –

The score for organization and presentation in the post test were 1.2 which was more than pretest score 0.8.

Conclusions –

It showed considerable improvement in the organization and presentation of their essays after the remedial measures.

5) **Criteria 5** – Originality and Creativity : 2 Marks

Table No.5	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	0.8	1.4

Interpretation –

The score for originality and creativity in the post test were 1.4 which was far better than the score of pretest which was 0.8 only.

Conclusions –

The above score showed that though creativity is an inherent trait yet training and practice can bring a certain degree of improvement in the area of originality and creativity as well.

Overall performance of Essay writing = Total Marks 10

Table No.6	No. of Students	Pretest Score Mean	Post Test Score Mean
	50	4.2	6.3

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Interpretation –

Above table showed pretest and post test mean score of all the students of std XII science.

Conclusions –

It showed considerable improvement in the pre-test score and post test score of std XII science students in writing Essays in English language.

Overall conclusions –

- 1) Students lacked reading practice and they had a poor vocabulary of English.
- 2) They were encouraged to refer to the books and magazines or periodicals available in the library in order to improve the vocabulary and develop the ability of creative thinking. It worked positively.

- 3) The guidance through training was given as remedial teaching. That helped to minimize errors, rectified grammatical structures, sharpen their thinking process through sensitive reading practice.

Suggestions –

- 1) Teachers should give exposure for public speaking skill, elocution skill of the students.
- 2) Teacher should conduct competitions of loud reading skill, which will help to improve correct pronunciation, dictation ability, voice modulation, speaking-reading in low-high pitch etc.
- 3) Teacher should give exposure to develop conversational skill through organizing group discussion, pair work etc.
- 4) The students should be encouraged to write informal letter so that their skill of writing, appreciation, presentation etc. can be developed.

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